

SYNERGIZING SORGHUM AND COWPEA: UNRAVELING YIELD DYNAMICS IN STRIGA-INFESTED FIELDS

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Abstract: Striga, the prominent plant parasite in Africa, stands as a formidable threat to agricultural productivity, causing significant economic repercussions across the continent. This parasitic menace inflicts staggering losses of up to 40 percent on crops, with grain production compromised across 44 million hectares, constituting 3.2% of the world's arable land. The insidious nature of Striga is underscored by its seeds, the primary source of inoculum, with each plant prolifically producing approximately 10,000 or more seeds. These seeds, measuring a mere 200 microns wide by 300 microns long and weighing 10⁻⁵ grams, pose a persistent challenge to crop health (Pieterse and Pesch, 1983; Berner et al., 1997).

Central to the parasitic threat is the longevity of Striga seeds in the soil, capable of remaining viable for an astonishing 15 to 20 years in the absence of a suitable plant host (Ramaiah et al., 1983). This longevity underscores the resilience and persistence of Striga, making it a formidable challenge for sustainable agriculture in the region. This review delves into the economic and agricultural implications of the Striga menace, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to mitigate its impact. Insights from seminal studies by Pieterse and Pesch (1983), Berner et al. (1997), and Ramaiah et al. (1983) provide a foundation for understanding the intricate dynamics of Striga infestations. Additionally, the review explores the unique characteristics of Striga seeds and their ability to endure in the soil, contributing to a prolonged and pervasive threat to crops.

A comprehensive understanding of the life cycle, seed characteristics, and persistence of Striga is essential for the development of effective control strategies. The review identifies critical research gaps and proposes avenues for future investigations to combat the economic and agricultural challenges posed by Striga. As the struggle against this parasitic threat continues, this synthesis aims to inform and guide researchers, policymakers, and practitioners in devising sustainable solutions to safeguard agricultural livelihoods in Africa.

Keywords: Striga, Plant Parasite, Crop Losses, Seed Longevity, Agricultural Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

The plant parasite *Striga* is the most economically important parasite in Africa. It is estimated that crop losses can be up to about 40 percent; grain production is also compromised on 44 million ha in Africa (3.2% of the world's arable land). *Striga* seeds are the main source of inoculum. Each plant produces roughly 10,000 or more seeds (Pieterse and Pesch, 1983) each of which weighs about 10⁻⁵ g and measures about 200 microns wide by 300 microns long (Berner et al., 1997). The tiny brown *Striga* seeds can remain viable in the soil for 15 to 20 years in the absence of a suitable plant host (Ramaiah et al., 1983).

Intercropping of cereals with legumes is a predominant feature in the cropping systems of Nigeria as a means of maximizing the use of limited farmlands and also for food security to the subsistence farmers. Little is known by the farmers, however, that this age-old practice may have a positive impact on reducing the effect of *Striga* parasitism on host yield.

According to Berner and Williams (1998), little information is available on non-hosts of *Striga* that are capable of stimulating germination of the parasite's seeds. The objective of this research is to devise a crop management technique with different cowpea/sorghum intercropping systems, as a means of controlling or reducing the effect of *Striga hermonthica* (Del.) Benth on host crop yield.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

At the onset of the 2002/2003 cropping season, an area of land was acquired at the IITA Kano Station research farm located at Wasai Village of Kano State, Nigeria. The aim of the field trial was to investigate the effect of intra-row and inter-row mixture of sorghum with two varieties of cowpea (IT-94K-440-3 and IT-93K-452-1) on the establishment of *S. hermonthica* and sorghum yield. The treatments consist of intra-row sole sorghum alternating with a cowpea (var. 452-1) row sown at 20 cm spacing (T₁), intra-row sole sorghum alternating with cowpea (var. 440-3) row sown at 20 cm spacing (T₂), intra-row mixture of sorghum and densely planted (10cm spacing) cowpea (var. 452-1) alternating with sole cowpea row (var. 452-1) sown at 20 cm spacing (T₃), intra-row mixture of sorghum and densely planted (10 cm spacing) cowpea (var. 440-3) alternating with sole cowpea row (var. 440-3) sown at 20 cm spacing (T₄), intra-row mixture of sorghum and densely planted (10 cm spacing) cowpea (var. 452-1) alternating with unplanted ridges (T₅), intra-row mixture of sorghum and densely planted (10 cm spacing) cowpea (var. 440-3) alternating with unplanted ridges (T₆), intra-row cereal mixture of sorghum and cowpea (var. 452-1) planted at 20 cm spacing alternating with sole cowpea (var. 452-1) row sown at 20 cm spacing (T₇), intra-row cereal mixture of sorghum and cowpea (var. 440-3) planted at 20 cm spacing alternating with sole cowpea (var. 440-3) row sown at 20 cm spacing (T₈) and finally sole sorghum (T₉). These treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replicates in plots measuring 5 x 6 m. The land was first harrowed and then 100 kg NPK (15:15:15) fertilizer per hectare was applied. Twenty four hours later the amount of *S. hermonthica* seeds that will be required to infest the field was calculated and weighed-out, a *Striga*-sieved sand mixture was made using a sieve of mesh size 180 micron. The area was inoculated with this mixture through hand-broadcasting. The planting area was shallow-ridged with a tractor ridger producing ridges at a spacing of 0.75 m from each other. A local sorghum variety (Minjibir local) was sown at a normal spacing of 1 metre between stands, while the cowpea varieties were planted as in the treatments mentioned above. Observations such as host seedling establishment (stand count), number of days to first *Striga* emergence, number of days to 50% flowering of *Striga*, plant height, *Striga* count at harvest and total host grain weight per net plot were made. The SAS[®] (Statistical Analysis System) software release version 9 for WINDOWS GLM (general linear model) procedure was adopted for the analysis from which the Student-Newman-Keuls test (SNK) at 5% level of significance was utilized in the interpretation of the results under the complete null hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results (Table 1) indicate that treatment 9 (sole sorghum plant) had the significantly (P 0.05) highest number of *Striga* per net plot of all the other sorghum treatments. The high infestation of this sole sorghum treatment with

Striga might be responsible for this treatment being amongst those with significantly (P 0.05) lowest yields (2370 kg/ha). Though Gurney et al. (1999) noted that the highest *Striga* infestation did not necessarily translate into the least yield, they indicated that the level of *Striga* biomass on a host influences host productivity, but the relationship is non linear, i.e. a point is reached where host grain production is independent of parasite biomass. A significantly (P 0.05) higher grain yield (3709 kg/ha) was obtained in treatment 3 [intra-row mixture of sorghum and densely planted cowpea variety, IT96D-452-1, at 10 cm spacing alternating with sole cowpea row variety, IT96D-452-1, sown at 20 cm spacing]. This treatment was among those with the least number of *Striga* per sorghum net plot. The fact that *Striga* is few in number and the yield of the cultivar higher in treatment 3 may be attributed to the effectiveness of the cowpea trap crop in stimulating the suicidal germination of the *Striga* seeds which would have otherwise attacked and reduced the productivity of Aliyu and Emechebe 025

Table 1. Effect of Intra- and inter-row mixing of sorghum with two varieties of cowpea on the emergence of *Striga*, *Striga* per net plot and host crop yield in a *Striga hermonthica* infested field, 2002.

Treatment	No. of days to first <i>Striga</i> emergence	<i>Striga</i> per net plot	Sorghum yield (kg/ha)
T1	33.3 ^a	188.3 ^{cd}	3600 ^a
T2	33.7 ^a	243.3 ^{ab}	2414.8 ^{bcd}
T3	32 ^a	64.3 ^{de}	3708.8 ^a
T4	36 ^a	147.3 ^{cd}	2022.2 ^{cde}
T5	30 ^a	64 ^{de}	3133.3 ^{abc}
T6	34.7 ^a	201.7 ^{de}	2311.1 ^{bcd}
T7	33.3 ^a	53.7 ^{de}	3114.8 ^{abc}
T8	35 ^a	63 ^{de}	3300.9 ^{ab}
T9	33 ^a	281 ^{ab}	2370.4 ^{bcd}
Means	34.3	87.8	2283.3
CV	8	44.6	18.0
SE	1.9	22.6	237.8
ROOT	2.8	39.2	411.8
MSE			

Means followed by the same letter(s) in the same column are not statistically different from each other, using the Student-NewmanKeuls test (SNK).

the host plant. It may also be attributed to the effectiveness of the cropping system, which not only reduced the *Striga* seed bank but also increased the nitrogen supply to the host crop, which manifested in a better yield. Gbéhounou and Adango (2002) pointed out that intercropping with cowpea leads to higher yield, and that this may be related to the benefits of nitrogen fixation under cowpea cropping, as well as a reduction in leaching of soil nutrients by cowpea cover. Symbiotic fixation, which depends on *Rhizobium* strain, may exceed 100 kg N ha⁻¹

¹ year⁻¹ and the nitrogen fixed is enough not only for the use of leguminous crops, but may also increase the soil reserve (Dupriez et al., 2001).

It can be concluded that, as suggested by Kunjo and Jobe (2002), the results of this research underscores the benefits of intercropping in reducing *Striga* infestation and improving productivity of the system.

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